

POLYMERS 2024

XIII. Slovak - Czech Conference

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

October 1-4, 2024, Stará Lesná, Slovakia

L-34: HYDROPHOBIC CARBON QUANTUM DOTS AS ANTIMICROBIAL AGENT IN POLYMER COATINGS AND THEIR ECO-TOXICITY STUDY

Mária Kováčová^a, Zdenko Špitálský^a, Mohamed Shaalan^{a,b}, Adriana Annušová^{a,c,d}, Veno Kononenko^e, Damjana Drobne^e

^a*Polymer Institute, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Dúbravská Cesta 9, 845 41, Bratislava, Slovakia; (m.kovacova@savba.sk)*

^b*Department of Pathology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Cairo University, Giza, 12211, Egypt*

^c*Institute of Physics, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Dúbravská Cesta 9, 845 41, Bratislava, Slovakia*

^d*Centre for Advanced Materials Application, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Dúbravská Cesta 9, 845 41, Bratislava, Slovakia*

^e*University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical faculty, Ljubljana, Slovenia*

The microbial contamination of the environment in which we are present, as well as the materials and devices with which we are constantly in touch, is currently a major problem due to the spread of an enormous number of diseases. Therefore, great efforts are being made to develop novel materials and methods for the prevention and treatment of diseases caused by microorganisms, and to disinfect surfaces and medical devices. Specifically, there is a global need for self-disinfecting plastics in various forms and areas. This research is focused on the preparation of antimicrobial polymer coatings doped with hydrophobic carbon quantum dots (hCQDs). The effectiveness of this material can be easily controlled using ordinary blue LEDs. Light-activated coatings generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) responsible for microbial eradication. Very important advantage of this approach is that bacteria cannot develop resistance to ROS. Treatment time is too short for bacteria to develop resistance. Furthermore, unlike conventional antibiotics, the oxygen radicals do not target a single site in the bacteria. ROS, such as singlet oxygen, superoxide, hydroxyl radical, produced by a hCQDs upon light irradiation attack various microbial cellular structures and metabolic pathways.

These nanoparticles are soluble in various organic solvents, and can therefore be easily mixed with a wide range of commercially-available polymer coatings, paints, etc. They have a high photostability, and are cost- and time-effective. Moreover, hCQDs have a low or no cytotoxicity, and are environmentally friendly. One of the decisive methods in terms of real use of the material is eco-toxicity study. It was performed using model organism – terrestrial isopod *Porcellio scaber*. For antibacterial testing, two bacteria were selected: *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Prepared material was also tested using several chemical-physical methods. Polymer coatings with hCQDs are the ideal material for many applications that require sterile surfaces, and can be used on almost any surface.

Acknowledgment: *This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe Framework Programme (grant agreement number 101058554), from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), and from the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) (grant number 10042534 & grant number 10055606) as part of the Horizon Europe [HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01]. The authors M.K. and Z.Š. are grateful to SRDA agency for financial support APVV-23-0325.*